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Maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality are major health problems in developing countries like India. Such is the magnitude of the problem that as per World Health Organization (WHO), 99% of all maternal deaths occur in developing countries (**Nour NM., 2008**).

There are certain categories of pregnancies where the mother and the fetus are at increased risk, and require extra attention and grand multiparity is one of them. Parity remains an important index in obstetric practice. The obstetric population is stratified using parity into nullipara, primipara, multipara, grand multipara and great grand multipara.

Grand multiparity is defined by the International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics (FIGO) as 5 deliveries or more, while the delivery of ten or more times is called great-grand multiparity (**Babinszki A et al., 1999; Bai et al., 2002; Afolabi et al., 2013; Njoku et al., 2017**) and this is a serious risk factor for poor pregnancy outcome because of the associated consequences to the mother and the fetus (**Odukogbe et al., 2001; Njoku et al., 2017**).

In his 1934 article, entitled 'The dangerous multiparae' (**Solomons B., 1934**), Bethel Solomons wrote: "My main object is to remove if possible, once for all, the idea that a primigravida means a difficult labor but a multipara means an easy one. It is altogether a mistake to suppose that in childbearing, practice makes perfect. "Solomons' concern for the multiparae was prompted by a study at that time from the Department of Health for Scotland which showed the maternal mortality rate associated with multiparity increasing "steadily and speedily" from the fifth pregnancy until women bearing their tenth child or more; had a mortality rate five times as high as all women bearing children.

The International Safe Motherhood Conference which was convened in Nairobi, Kenya, in 1987, to address the appalling high maternal death rates in developing countries, identified grand multiparity as a definite risk, with a high score of 2 out of a maximum of 3, which depends on their potential impact on the outcome of pregnancy (**Rayamajhi., 2006**).

In developed countries, grand multiparity is on the brink of extinction, with an incidence of 1% - 4% of all births while in developing countries like India, the incidence of grand multiparity is much higher. This is of great concern because

when added to the existing burden of low socioeconomic status and poor accessibility to emergency obstetric care, it significantly increases the risk to the mother and fetus with resultant feto-maternal morbidities and mortalities (**Ogedengbe et al.2003; Ogbe et al., 2010; Njoku et al., 2017**). In addition, effective family planning measures, increased level of education and desensitization of women to old cultural and religious beliefs and stigmas of small family size can reduce the incidence of grand multiparity and its associated consequences (**D'souza et al., 2011**).

Grand multiparity is becoming less of concern in the developed countries with low prevalence due to family counselling, planning and because of the widespread usage of contraceptive practice while in the developing countries it is still of a great concern and still high in prevalence. In India, grand multiparity is common due to cultural beliefs, gender preferences, poor female literacy, social deprivation, social habits in the society and marriage at a young age.

The complications of pregnancy in the grand multipara are diabetes, hypertension, antepartum and post-partum hemorrhage, dysfunctional labor, feto-pelvic disproportion, increased risk of abortions, multiple pregnancy,

abruptio placentae, placenta previa, malpresentation, anemia, macrosomic babies, pre-term labor, uterine rupture, increased rate of instrumental delivery, puerperal infections, congenital malformations and perinatal mortality (**Maymon et al.,1998; Bai et al., 2002; Severinski N et al., 2009; Shechter et al., 2010; Omole-Ohonsi et al., 2011; Mgaya et al., 2013; Al Shaikh et al.,2017**) .

The chance of caesarean section is high due to malpresentation, malposition, cephalo-pelvic disproportion (CPD) etc. (**Shahid et al., 2009**). High rate of caesarean section can also be due to failure of descent of the presenting part during the first stage and arrest of cervical dilatation (**Rizwan et al., 2009**).

There is a high incidence of rupture of uterus in grand multiparous women and frequently, they are admitted in a moribund state resulting in increased mortality and morbidity (**Khan A., 1997**). As the situation is seen in the older women, medical as well as gynecological conditions are seen to complicate these pregnancies more than those of lower parity.

More recent reports, however, have demonstrated that in the presence of good perinatal care, grand multiparity no longer needs to be considered an obstetrical risk in the presence of satisfactory health care conditions (**Kumari et al., 2002**;

Kaplan et al., 1995). Most of the studies argued that grand multiparas are more likely to be of old age which might be the reason for increased morbidity and mortality. In clinical practice, such factor is difficult to be removed because women's age is the most important biological variable that influences the reproductive events which we study.

There is a significant incidence of grand multiparity in India, therefore in this study we aimed to determine the prevalence, fetal and maternal outcomes in grand multiparous women, in a tertiary care hospital in north India.

Pregnancy after fourth delivery is viewed with anxiety, especially by obstetricians in developing countries, working under difficult conditions and with limited facilities. The complications that occur to these patients during pregnancy, at the time of delivery, and in the puerperium warrants them special attention, first of all, the ordinary complications of pregnancy and child birth are increased in this group of women, secondly, since such complications tend to be more common in the lower socioeconomic groups, their ill-effects have a far reaching impact on the patients affecting due to poverty, lack of facilities and the usual accompanying delayed presentation to medical personnel. Moreover,

these patients usually lack medical education, they are undernourished and almost always overworked, with usually poor antenatal care.

Sociological factors play a very important part, for the majority of these patients are poor , overworked and tired, many of them have never regained a good blood picture, and anemia may drag them from one pregnancy to the next without respite, they tend to feed their numerous children at the expense of their own nutrition, so that they are consequently often very short of vitamins and first class proteins, they are too busy to attend to their health, and due to the rapid succession of pregnancies and long periods of lactation they are likely to become depleted from calcium.

The literature is full of conflicting reports on outcomes of high parity pregnancy. There is no adequate number of studies performed about it in India, therefore such a study is needed. The main point of interest for obstetricians in a case of grand multiparity is how this might alter labour and delivery expectations, in addition to the risk of maternal and fetal morbidity and mortality.

The studies in the literature that associate high parity with increased maternal and fetal adverse outcomes are diverse in their findings. The differences in foeto-maternal mortality by parity have been partly associated with lower health services coverage among the high parity births. It was observed that there was a trend toward lower utilization of maternal health services by mothers as the birth order increases, especially institutional delivery and skilled birth attendance (**Sonneveldt., 2013**). In addition, several confounders played out in the high parity literature. Most of such reports attributed adverse obstetric outcomes to high parity (**Mgaya et al., 2013; Ogedengbe et al., 2003**). Meanwhile, socioeconomic status, maternal age, nutritional status, standard of maternal health care, and health-seeking behavior are known to affect the obstetric performance. These factors operate at different degrees in different individual mothers and different settings, and in some cases, in combinations, to influence the obstetric outcome. Again, methodological differences are very important. For instance, some of the reports came from cross-sectional study that is weak in assessing causality (**Rizwan et al., 2009; Ogedengbe et al., 2003**).

In developed economies with excellent obstetric facilities, standard perinatal care and wholesome health-seeking behavior, the prevailing reports indicate

that obstetric complications among grand multipara are now independently associated with progressive maternal age and not parity (**Kenny et al., 2013**).

Unlike the rich-resource settings with satisfactory outcomes in developed countries, where these confounders are either nonexistent or reduced to an insignificant level; in poor-resource settings, there are increased adverse obstetric outcomes in high parity pregnancy.

*REVIEW OF
LITERATURE*

Severinski N *et al.*, (2009) in a retrospective analysis of 22504 women, delivered at a tertiary healthcare center in Croatia, where grand multiparas were compared with multiparas; concluded that grand multiparas were more likely to be older, unmarried or divorced, less educated, unemployed, and to have received less prenatal care than the multiparas. Labor complications were similar between the two groups, but the caesarean delivery rate was significantly higher in grand multiparas. Mean duration of labor was similar between the two groups, but prolonged labor of more than 24 hours was more frequent, mean birth weight was significantly lower for neonates, higher incidence of low Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes, higher late fetal mortality, but a lower incidence of major congenital anomalies and neonatal mortality was seen in grand multiparas.

Omole-Ohonsi A and Ashimi AO (2011) conducted a 5-year prospective observational study of cases and concluded a higher prevalence of GDM, PIH, heart disease, anemia, APH, malpresentation, macrosomia and CPD in grand multiparas compared to multiparas. However, several factors like good antenatal care and delivery services, increased patient's awareness and an efficient blood banking system reduced the pregnancy risks of grand multiparity similar to that of women of lower parity.

Ahmed IAM (2013) conducted a prospective case-control study of 450 deliveries and concluded that main complications of grand multiparas were antenatal; they had significantly higher incidence of hypertension, anemia, multiple pregnancy, DM, malpresentation, and ante-partum hemorrhage. Most of the grand multiparas delivered normally with less use of instrumental delivery, emergency caesarean section, and overall less complicated labor. They delivered significantly macrosomic babies with significantly higher incidence of macerated still births. Maternal deaths, emergency caesarean sections, PPH, and instrumental deliveries, genital tract injuries were increased in multiparas' group.

Alsammani MA and Ahmed SR (2015) studied 8040 deliveries in Saudi Arabia and found the prevalence of grand multiparity to be 5.3%. There was a higher frequency of medical disorders, increased risk of caesarean sections, less of instrumental deliveries in grand multiparas.

Lal R et al., (2015) did a study on 8304 deliveries conducted over a period of one year in Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, Ranchi, out of which 5.08% (422) cases were grand multiparas. Grand multiparous women were compared with

controls, with lesser parity. Mean age of cases was 30 years, most of them were of low socioeconomic status and unbooked. Complications found significantly associated with grand multiparity were uterine rupture, caesarean section, anemia, hypertension and diabetes.

Roy R and Vernekar M (2017) found a prevalence of 0.72% of GMP in 15,196 deliveries studied. The prevalence was higher in lower socio-economic class, less educated, Muslims, married at an early age. The significant complications of grand multiparity were anemia, PIH/pre-eclampsia, oligohydramnios, preterm pregnancy, APH, PROM, malpresentation, prolonged second stage of labor, obstructed labor, rupture uterus and primary PPH.

Njoku CO et al., (2017) conducted a prospective case-control study comparing 150 grand multiparous women (cases) with 150 multi-parous women (controls) matched for age and admitted for delivery. Grand multiparity was higher among women who were Muslims, with less or no education. Among complications, PIH and primary postpartum hemorrhage was more common in grand multiparas. The mean packed cell volume at delivery was significantly lower in grand multiparous women than multiparas.

Akhtar R et al., (2017), in a descriptive study of 680 grand multiparous women inferred that GMP comprised 15% of total obstetric admissions and 15.4% of total births. Grand multiparity was significantly associated with low educational status, poor pre-natal care and increased maternal age. Complications in these women included anemia, hypertension, malpresentation, diabetes, PPH, obstructed and dysfunctional labor, rupture uterus.

Al-Shaikh GK et al., (2017) conducted a cohort study on 3327 women which showed that grand multiparous Saudi females had similar rates of maternal and neonatal complications compared to multiparas, after matching was done for confounders like age, socio economic status and peri-natal care.

Alhainiah MH et al., (2018) did a retrospective study of 928 deliveries performed at a tertiary center in Saudi Arabia, and compared primiparas to grand multiparas, in which it was concluded that the average fetal weight of the neonates of grand multiparas was higher. GDM, anemia, other medical disorders, ROM, IUGR, and PPH was significantly more prevalent in grand multiparas.

Ajong AB et al., (2019) conducted a retrospective chart review of 1755 delivery records in Oku and determined an 8-year prevalence of GMP of 27%, with no significant difference in adverse maternal outcomes such as PPH, dystocia, caesarean section, and PROM among grand multiparas compared to primiparas and multiparas. However, GMPs were less likely to develop second to fourth degree perineal tears compared to women with lesser parity. There was no significant difference between the groups in fetal outcomes.

Eugene MI and Abedinego OA (2019) did an age-matched case-control study in Nigeria, comparing grand multiparity with multiparity. The only significant difference between the two groups was abnormal lie, which was more common in grand multiparas. The two groups were comparable in perinatal and maternal adverse outcomes.

Muniro Z et al., (2019) did a retrospective cross-sectional study in Northern Tanzania and found an overall prevalence of 9.44% of grand multiparity from the year 2006 to 2014. The study demonstrated a higher risk of pre-labour rupture of membranes, stillbirth and preterm delivery in grand multiparas as compared to women of lower parity.

Smith K and Philips R (2019), in a retrospective five-year study found the prevalence of GMP of 1.4%, with a significant association with educational status, occupation and lack of contraceptive use. APH and hypertensive disorders, PPH, blood transfusion, wound infection, caesarean section, still births, LBW, Special Care Baby Unit admissions were significantly associated with grand multiparas.

*AIMS
AND
OBJECTIVES*

- To determine the prevalence of grand multiparity.
- To study the maternal outcomes of grand-multiparous pregnancies.
- To study the fetal outcomes of grand-multiparous pregnancies.

*MATERIAL
AND
METHODS*

- **Study Design:** Prospective case-control hospital-based study

- **Study Area:** After obtaining approval from the hospital ethical committee, the study was conducted in the department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of SMGS Hospital, Government Medical College, Jammu. It is a tertiary care hospital, run by government where medical care is given free of charge to pregnant women and it caters for the population of Jammu province.

- **Study Population:** All grand multiparous women who got admitted in the Obstetrics & Gynaecology Department of Government Medical College & Hospital, Jammu from November 2019 to October 2020 and fulfilled the inclusion criteria for the study, were taken as cases. They were compared with an equal number of primigravidas or multiparous women, who formed the control group, chosen by taking every next woman who got admitted after a grand multipara.

➤ **Inclusion Criteria:**

- Woman with 5th to 9th pregnancy of more than 24 weeks of gestation was taken as a case.
- Woman with 1st to 4th pregnancy of more than 24 weeks of gestation was taken as a control.
- Willingness to participate in the study.

➤ **Exclusion Criteria:**

- Woman with pre-existing medical conditions such as chronic hypertension, diabetes mellitus, cardiac disease, renal disease, connective tissue disorder, seizure disorder, etc.
- Refusal to participate in the study.

➤ **Data Collection:** Detailed history was taken, and examination was done of cases and controls. Examination of the patient included GPE, examination of cardiovascular system, respiratory system, per abdomen and per vaginum examination. Blood pressure was measured using the auscultatory method with a standard calibrated, validated instrument. An appropriate sized cuff was used to ensure accuracy, Korotkoff sound

5 was taken to measure diastolic BP. Routine antenatal investigation were done-

- Hemoglobin
- ABO and Rh grouping
- Bleeding Time
- Clotting Time
- Blood sugar
- HIV
- VDRL
- HBsAg
- Platelet count
- PT
- PTI
- LFTs
- RFTs
- Urine for albumin
- 24 hr urine for protein
- USG for fetal well-being and liquor volume

Paper medical records were used to ascertain women's medical status throughout the gestation. During labor, patients were managed according

to hospital's protocol and partograph recordings were used to evaluate the progress of labor. The intrapartum complications including prolonged labor, intrapartum hemorrhage, uterine rupture and mode of delivery were also recorded. After delivery, information on birth weight, Apgar scores and admission to neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) were obtained. Patients were monitored for 24 hours for primary postpartum hemorrhage. Also, data on maternal mortality, stillbirth and fetal malformation were obtained. Length of stay in the hospital was noted. Then, these women were followed up six weeks after delivery.

- **Statistical Analysis:** The recorded data was compiled and entered in a spreadsheet (Microsoft Excel) and then exported to data editor of SPSS Version 20.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). Statistical software SPSS (version 20.0) and Microsoft Excel were used to carry out the statistical analysis of data. Continuous variables were expressed as Mean \pm SD and categorical variables were summarized as percentages. Student's independent t-test was employed for comparing continuous variables. Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, whichever appropriate, was used for comparison of categorical variables. Graphically the data was presented

by bar diagrams. A P-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All P-values were two tailed.

*OBSERVATIONS
&
RESULTS*

The present observational prospective case- control study was conducted on all the grand multiparous women who got admitted in Government Medical College & Hospital, Jammu from November 2019 to October 2020 and fulfilled the inclusion criteria for the study. They were compared with an equal number of women with 1st to 4th viable pregnancy. The controls were chosen by taking every next woman who got admitted after a grand multipara. Following observations were made during the culmination of the study:

PREVALENCE OF GRAND MULTIPARITY

During the study period of 1 year, out of a total of 26,535 parturients in the labour room, 205 were grand multiparas. The prevalence of grand multiparity calculated was 0.77% (7.7725 per 1000 deliveries).

Figure 1 Pie Diagram showing prevalence of grand multi-parity

For the purpose of this study, only 187 grand multiparous women fulfilled the inclusion criteria. Therefore, only these cases were compared with 187 controls.

AGE DISTRIBUTION

The mean age of the grand-multiparous women was 31.6 ± 4.23 years, and that of non grand-multiparous control group was 26.2 ± 3.79 years. The ages of cases ranged from 21 to 42 years, while those of controls ranged from 20 to 41 years. Majority (69%) of females in cases were in the age group of 30-42 years, whereas most of (79.7%) the females in controls were in the age group of 20-29 years. Stratification of the study population according to age showed that grand multiparous females were more likely to be of advanced age with P-value <0.001 , and therefore, significant.

Age (Years)	Cases		Controls		P-value
	No.	%age	No.	%age	
20-24	9	4.8	62	33.2	<0.001*
25-29	49	26.2	87	46.5	
30-34	72	38.5	32	17.1	
≥ 35	57	30.5	6	3.2	
Total	187	100	187	100	
Mean \pm SD (Range)	31.6 \pm 4.23 (20-42)		26.2 \pm 3.79 (20-41)		

*Statistically Significant Difference (P-value<0.05)

Fig 2: Age distribution of cases and controls

GESTATIONAL AGE AT THE TIME OF DELIVERY:

Grand multiparous women were more likely to deliver at an earlier gestational age as compared to women with lower parity, with a significant P-value of 0.004. The mean gestational age at delivery was 37.16 ± 3.282 weeks for cases and 38.24 ± 1.849 weeks for the controls.

Table 2: Gestational age at the time of delivery in cases and controls					
Group	N	Mean	SD	Range	P-value
Cases	187	37.16	3.282	26-42	0.004*
Controls	187	38.24	1.849	31.9-41.9	

**Statistically Significant Difference (P-value<0.05)*

Fig 3. Gestational age at the time of delivery in cases and controls

ONSET OF LABOUR:

Majority of the patients in both the groups (59% in cases and 54.5% in controls) went into spontaneous labour, followed by those in which labour was induced (23% in cases, 22.5% in controls), patients for elective LSCS (12.8% in cases, 19.8% in controls) and who underwent emergency LSCS (4.3% in cases, 3.2% in controls). Mode of onset of labour was similar in both the groups.

Table 3: Mode of onset of labour in cases and controls					
Mode of onset of labour	Cases		Controls		P-value
	No.	%age	No.	%age	
Spontaneous	112	59.9	102	54.5	0.316
Induced	43	23.0	42	22.5	
Elective LSCS	24	12.8	37	19.8	
Emergency LSCS	8	4.3	6	3.2	
Total	187	100	187	100	

Fig 4. Mode of onset of labour in cases and controls

MODE OF DELIVERY:

Most of the grand multiparous women (65.2%) in this study delivered vaginally, while in the control group, the most common mode of delivery was Caesarean section (58.3%). This difference showed a significant P-value of <0.001. One of the grand multiparous women had to undergo laparotomy for delivery with repair of uterine rupture and one required Caesarean hysterectomy for badly ruptured uterus.

Table 4: Mode of delivery in cases and controls					
Mode of delivery	Cases		Controls		P-value
	No.	%age	No.	%age	
Vaginal	122	65.2	78	41.7	<0.001*
C section	63	33.7	109	58.3	
Laparotomy	1	0.5	0	0.0	
Caesarean Hysterectomy	1	0.5	0	0.0	
Total	187	100	187	100	

*Statistically Significant Difference (P-value<0.05)

Fig 5. Mode of delivery in cases and controls

ANTENATAL COMPLICATIONS:

Table 5. Antenatal Complications in cases & controls					
Maternal complications	Cases		Controls		P-value
	No.	%age	No.	%age	
Severe anaemia	16	8.6	3	1.6	0.005*
Preterm labour	16	8.6	12	6.4	0.432
Cholestasis	2	1.1	8	4.3	0.109
PPROM	9	4.8	10	5.3	0.814
Gestational hypertension	19	10.2	8	4.3	0.028*
Pre eclampsia	1	0.5	0	0.0	1.000
Imminent eclampsia	3	1.6	2	1.1	0.653
Eclampsia	8	4.3	1	0.5	0.043*
HELLP Syndrome	3	1.6	0	0.0	0.248
GDM	3	1.6	1	0.5	0.623
Placenta previa	4	2.1	2	1.1	0.681
Abruptio placentae	1	0.5	0	0.0	1.000
APH	3	1.6	2	1.1	0.653
Malpresentation	14	7.5	16	8.6	0.703
Multiple pregnancy	9	4.8	2	1.1	0.066
Oligohydramnios	12	6.4	9	4.8	0.501
Polyhydramnios	0	0.0	1	0.5	1.000
Post Datism	22	11.76	18	9.63	0.503

*Statistically Significant Difference (P-value<0.05)

The antenatal complications in cases and controls were compared. Out of all these complications, grand multiparas were more likely to develop severe anemia (p-value 0.005), gestational hypertension (p-value 0.028) and eclampsia (p-value 0.043) as compared to women with lower parity, with a significant difference. The comparison of other antenatal complications in the two groups did not reach a difference of statistical significance.

Fig 6B. Antepartum Complications in Cases & Controls

INTRA-PARTUM COMPLICATIONS:

Table 6. Intrapartum complications in cases & controls					
Maternal complications	Cases		Controls		P-value
	No.	%age	No.	%age	
Failed induction	3	1.6	3	1.6	1.000
NPOL	6	3.2	3	1.6	0.498
Non descent at full dilatation	2	1.1	1	0.5	1.000
Compound Presentation	6	3.2	0	0.0	0.031*
Obstructed Labour	3	1.6	0	0.0	0.248
C-Section	67	35.83	78	41.71	0.243
Uterine rupture	3	1.6	0	0.0	0.248
Caesarean Hysterectomy	1	0.5	0	0.0	1.000

*Statistically Significant Difference (P-value<0.05)

During labour, the grand multiparas were more likely to have compound presentation as compared to non grand multiparas, with a significant p value of 0.031. The compound presentations seen in grand multiparas were hand prolapse (in 3 cases) and cord prolapse (in 3 cases). The other intra partum complications in the two groups were not of statistical significance. There were 3 cases of obstructed labour and 3 of uterine rupture in grand multiparas, and none in the control group.

Fig 7. Intrapartum Complications in Cases & Controls

POST-PARTUM COMPLICATIONS:

Table 7. Postpartum complications in cases & controls					
Maternal complications	Cases		Controls		P-value
	No.	%age	No.	%age	
PPH	6	3.2	0	0.0	0.031*
Puerperial Sepsis	2	1.1	1	0.5	1.000

*Statistically Significant Difference (P-value<0.05)

In the post-partum period, the complication that happened more in grand multiparas was post-partum hemorrhage. The difference of incidence in the two groups was statistically significant with a p-value of 0.031. Puerperial sepsis, although seen more in grand multiparas did not show a significant difference in the two groups.

REQUIREMENT OF BLOOD

A marked difference was found in cases and controls with respect to the requirement of blood transfusion, with more of grand multiparous women requiring transfusions compared to their controls. The P-value calculated was highly significant <0.001 .

Table 8. Requirement of blood transfusion in cases and controls					
Blood transfusion	Cases		Controls		P-value
	No.	%age	No.	%age	
Given	26	13.9	6	3.2	$<0.001^*$
Not given	161	86.1	181	96.8	
Total	187	100	187	100	

**Statistically Significant Difference (P-value <0.05)*

Fig 9. Requirement of blood transfusion in cases and controls

DURATION OF STAY IN THE HOSPITAL

Table 9. Duration of hospital stay in cases and controls					
Hospital stay (Days)	Cases		Controls		P-value
	No.	%age	No.	%age	
< 3 Days	108	57.8	103	55.1	0.379
3-7 Days	70	37.4	83	44.4	
> 7 Days	9	4.8	1	0.5	
Total	187	100	187	100	
Mean ± SD (Range)	2.9±1.93 (1-14)		2.8±1.34 (1-8)		

Duration of stay in the hospital was not significantly different in cases and controls. In both the groups, most of the patients had to stay for less than 3 days (57.8% in cases and 55.1% in controls). Mean duration of stay in grand multiparas and non grand multiparous women was 2.9 ± 1.93 days and 2.8 ± 1.34 days, respectively.

Fig 10: Duration of hospital stay in cases and controls

PERINATAL OUTCOME:

APGAR Score:

With regard to neonatal outcome of cases and controls, the Apgar score at 1st minute of birth was compared. The grand multiparas were more likely to have a lower APGAR (<7) at 1st minute, as compared to women with lower parity. This difference in outcome was statistically highly significant with P-value <0.001. The mean value of 1st minute Apgar score in cases and controls was 8.7 ± 2.15 and 9.5 ± 1.27 respectively.

Table 10. APGAR score at 1 minute in cases and controls					
APGAR score	Cases		Controls		P-value
	No.	%age	No.	%age	
< 7	22	13.1	8	4.4	<0.001*
≥ 7	146	86.9	175	95.6	
Total	168	100	183	100	
Mean ± SD (Range)	8.7±2.15 (2-10)		9.5±1.27 (2-10)		

**Statistically Significant Difference (P-value<0.05)*

Grand multiparous women were more likely to have a lower Apgar score at 5 minutes (<7) compared to non grand multiparas, with a highly significant P-value of <0.001.

Table 11. APGAR score at 5 minutes in cases and controls					
APGAR score	Cases		Controls		P-value
	No.	%age	No.	%age	
< 7	18	10.7	4	2.2	<0.001*
≥ 7	150	89.3	179	97.8	
Total	168	100	183	100	
Mean±SD (Range)	8.9±1.98 (2-10)		9.7±1.13 (2-10)		

*Statistically Significant Difference (P-value<0.05)

Fig 12: Apgar score at 5 minutes in cases and controls

BIRTH WEIGHT

Table 12. Birth weight (kg) of neonates in cases and controls					
Birth weight (Kg)	N	Mean	SD	Range	P-value
Cases	187	2.76	0.659	0.7-4.5	0.439
Controls	187	2.81	0.469	1.5-4.5	

Birth weight was comparable in cases and controls, and there was no significant difference between the two groups. Mean birth weight in cases was 2.76 ± 0.659 kg and in controls was 2.81 ± 0.469 kg.

PERINATAL COMPLICATIONS:

Table 13. Perinatal Complications in cases & controls					
Perinatal complications	Cases		Controls		P-value
	No.	%age	No.	%age	
Preterm	46	24.6	28	15.0	0.019*
IUFD	19	10.2	4	2.1	0.003*
Early Neonatal Death	14	7.5	5	2.7	0.034*
ARDS	7	3.7	4	2.1	0.541
MAS	6	3.2	3	1.6	0.498
Macrosomia	10	5.3	4	2.1	0.173
LBW	31	16.6	17	9.1	0.031*
Neonatal Jaundice	7	3.7	2	1.1	0.177
IUGR	6	3.2	8	4.3	0.586

**Statistically Significant Difference (P-value<0.05)*

After comparing perinatal complications in cases and controls, it was found that cases were more likely to develop these complications, out of which preterm birth (p-value 0.019), intra uterine death (p-value 0.003), early neonatal death (p-value 0.034) and low birth weight (p-value 0.031) were statistically significant.

ADMISSION IN NEONATAL ICU:

Table14. NICU admission in babies of cases and controls					
NICU admission	Cases		Controls		P-value
	No.	%age	No.	%age	
Yes	32	17.1	18	9.6	0.034*
No	155	82.9	169	90.4	
Total	187	100	187	100	

**Statistically Significant Difference (P-value<0.05)*

Neonatal ICU admissions were required more in grand multiparous women as compared to non grand multiparas, with a statistically significant p-value of 0.034.

Fig 15. NICU admission in cases and controls

DURATION OF STAY IN NEONATAL ICU:

Table 15. Duration of stay in NICU among cases and controls				
Duration of stay in NICU (Days)	Mean	SD	Range	P-value
Cases	5.1	4.91	1-18	0.697
Controls	4.5	3.26	1-12	

Duration of stay in NICU, of cases and controls was compared and there was no statistically significant difference between the two. The mean duration of stay in NICU was longer for neonates of grand multiparas (5.1 days) than of non grand multiparas (4.5 days).

Fig 16. Duration of stay in NICU among cases and controls

DISCUSSION

This study was a prospective case control study, comparing obstetric and neonatal outcomes between grand multiparas and women with lower parity, who were delivered in the department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology in Government Medical College, Jammu.

The prevalence of grand multiparity calculated in this study was 0.77%. This is concordant with the 0.72% prevalence found in the study conducted by **Roy R et al., (2017)** in Kolkata. However, **Lal et al., (2015)** calculated a higher prevalence of 5.08% in Jharkhand.

Prevalence of grand multiparity from African and Middle East countries is much higher, as seen in studies by **Muniro et al., (2019)**, **Ajong et al., (2019)** and **Alhainiah et al., (2018)** to be 9.44%, 27% and 31.7%, respectively. This can be explained by the difference in cultural, socio economic and educational backgrounds. Also, adoption of family planning methods, Government encouragement towards small family norm and National Health Mission propaganda in India could have been the cause for a lower prevalence in our study. Another plausible explanation can be the overall decreased admission rate during the study period because of COVID-19 pandemic.

The mean age of study population in this study was 31.6 ± 4.23 years, as compared to 26.2 ± 3.79 years in controls (Table 1). Most of the cases (69%) were in the age group of 30-42 years and most of the (79.7%) controls were in the age group of 20-29 years.

Ajong et al., (2019) found that the mean age of cases was 33.4 ± 5.0 years and of controls was 23.2 ± 4.6 years. **Lal et al., (2015)** found the mean age to be 30 years in cases and 25 years in controls. The mean age found by **Teguete et al., (2012)** was 34.1 and 26.1 years in cases and controls respectively. In all these studies, the grand multiparas were found to be significantly older than controls, which can be expected due to their higher parity. Our study results, with respect to differences in ages of grand multiparas and non grand multiparas, were consistent with all these studies.

Grand multiparas were found to deliver at a significantly lower gestational age compared to non grand multiparas, in this study. The mean gestational age at delivery was 37.16 ± 3.282 weeks for cases and 38.24 ± 1.849 weeks for controls, with a significant P-value (Table 2).

Studies conducted by **Alhainiah et al., (2018)**, **Al-Shaikh et al., (2017)** and **Njoku et al., (2017)** found that the mean gestational age at delivery of grand multiparas was lower than that of women with lower parity, but none among them showed a significant P-value. However, **Alsammani et al., (2015)** found a significant P-value of 0.001, where the mean gestational ages of cases and controls were 38.4556 ± 1.75 and 38.0695 ± 2.00 weeks respectively, which is in accordance to our study.

The mode of onset of labour in our study was similar in the two groups, with majority of patients going into spontaneous labour (59.9% in cases and 54.5% in controls) followed by those in whom labour was induced (23% in cases and 22.5% in controls), as seen in Table 3. Majority (65.2%) cases delivered vaginally while majority (58.3%) controls delivered by Caesarean section, with a statistically significant difference (Table 4).

Similar result was seen by **Al-Shaikh et al., (2017)** with P-value <0.01 where cases were less likely to deliver by Caesarean section. **Akhtar et al., (2017)** also found vaginal delivery to be the most common mode of delivery in grand multiparas, where 79.12% delivered vaginally and 17.06% underwent C-section. **Eugene et al., (2019)** and **Ajong et al., (2019)** found a lower incidence of Caesarean section in cases but P-value was not significant for comparison with controls.

In contrast to this, **Smith et al., (2019)** found a higher risk of Caesarean section in grand multiparas (P-value 0.032). Also, **Alhainiah et al., (2018)** and **Njoku et al., (2017)** found a higher incidence of C-section in cases, but none among them could reach a significant P-value.

The most significant antenatal complication seen more in grand multiparous women as compared to women with lower parity, in this study, was severe anemia (Hb <7 gm.%). The P-value calculated was 0.005 (Table 5).

Most of the previous studies on grand multiparity have found a significant association of grand multiparity with anemia. **Smith et al., (2019)**, **Roy R et al., (2017)** and **Akhtar et al., (2017)** found anemia as the commonest antenatal complication in 47.1%, 59.1% and 70.15% grand multiparous subjects respectively. Also, **Shechter et al., (2010)** found a linear association between parity and anemia. This may be attributed to the significant amount of blood loss during each delivery.

Our study found an increased risk of gestational hypertension and eclampsia in grand multiparous women, with significant association. Overall, a higher incidence of all hypertensive disorders of pregnancy was found in cases in comparison to controls.

Our result was consistent with **Smith et al., (2019)** and **Al-Shaikh et al., (2017)**. **Lal et al., (2015)** also found a higher incidence of hypertension in grand multiparas as compared to non grand multiparas (43% vs. 14%). Gestational hypertension was the second most common complication seen in cases by **Akhtar et al., (2017)**, whereas PIH, pre-eclampsia and eclampsia together formed the second most common complication seen in grand multiparas, by **Roy R et al., (2017)**. Similarly, **Ahmed IAM (2013)** compared grand multiparas with multiparas and found a significantly higher risk of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, in grand multiparas.

Mgaya et al., (2013) found the prevalence of hypertension to be higher in grand multiparas but without significant differences when adjusted for age.

Besides anemia and hypertension, the other antenatal complications were not significantly associated with grand multiparity in our study. These complications included preterm labour, cholestasis, PPRM, GDM, placenta previa, abruption placentae, APH, malpresentation, multiple pregnancy, oligohydramnios, polyhydramnios and post datism. Although multiple pregnancy was seen more in cases than controls, but the difference did not reach statistical significance.

There are many conflicting reports on complications in high parity pregnancies. **Muniro et al., (2019)** reported a significant association of prelabour rupture of membranes with grand multiparity. In contrast to this, **Alhainiah et al., (2018)** reported a higher incidence of PROM in primiparas compared to grand multiparas while preterm labour was found equally in both the groups.

Al-Shaikh et al., (2017) and **Mgaya et al., (2013)** saw GDM more frequently in grand multiparas. However, in regression models controlling for age, grand multiparity was not associated with higher risk of gestational diabetes. This was in accordance with our study. **Shahida et al., (2011)** found a significantly higher incidence of gestational diabetes in grand multiparas (12% vs. 2%).

Alhainiah (2018) reported placenta previa and abruptio placentae more commonly in grand multiparas but without statistical significance. **Njoku et al., (2017)** found the incidence of antepartum hemorrhage to be comparable between the two groups. Similar findings were supported by our study.

Ahmed IAM (2013) reported a significantly higher incidence of breech presentation and transverse lie in grand multiparas as compared to multiparas. **Eugene et al., (2019)** also found a higher risk of fetal abnormal lie in grand multiparas. However, this study did not find any difference in the cases and controls with respect to malpresentations. Results, similar to our study, were seen by **Simonsen et al., (2015)**.

Roy R et al., (2017) found an incidence of 3.6% of twin pregnancies in grand multiparas and oligohydramnios as the third most common complication. However, our study did not find any significant association of multiple pregnancies and amniotic fluid disorders with parity. This may be explained by the small sample size in our study.

Among the intrapartum complications, our study found significantly high risk of compound presentations in cases (Table 6). The compound presentations seen were hand prolapse, in 3 cases, and cord prolapse, in 3 cases.

Three cases and none among controls reported with obstructed labour to our hospital, but results were not significantly associated with grand multiparity. All these cases had taken a trial of labour outside the hospital and later presented with obstructed labour due to cephalo-pelvic disproportion. In congruence with this, no significant association of cephalo-pelvic disproportion/ obstructed labour with parity was seen by **Eugene et al, (2019)**.

Three cases were admitted with uterine rupture. One among them had to undergo Caesarean hysterectomy and two were repaired. Probably due to a small scale design with inability to capture rare adverse events, this difference in the cases and controls of obstructed labour and uterine rupture did not reach a statistical significance. Rupture of uterus was quite frequently seen in grand multiparas as compared to control group (15% vs. 1%) by **Lal et al., (2015)**.

Grand multiparous women were more prone to post-partum hemorrhage in this study, with a significant P-value of 0.031 (Table 7). **Smith et al., (2019)**, **Alhainiah et al., (2018)** and **Njoku et al., (2017)** also found PPH more frequently in grand multiparas. **Munim et al., (2000)** found a three times higher risk of PPH in cases as compared to controls.

This may be attributable to unstable gravid uterus due to lax anterior abdominal wall and uterine muscles from repeated pregnancies and overstretching of the muscles by the enlarged gravid uterus.

Contradictory to our study, **Muniro et al., (2019)** and **Ajong et al., (2019)** did not find any significant association of PPH with grand multiparity.

Puerperial sepsis was seen comparably in both the groups in this study, similar to the findings by **Njoku et al., (2017)**.

A highly significant association of grand multiparous women was found with the need for blood transfusions (Table 8). This can be explained by a high incidence of anemia in the cases, with further blood loss in repeated deliveries, and a high frequency of post-partum hemorrhage seen in them. In the study done by **Smith et al., (2019)**, around 45.1% of the grand multiparous women received blood transfusion which gave a significant association of parity with the need for blood transfusions.

Both the cases and controls had a similar duration of around 3 days of stay in the hospital in the current study (Table 9). Most of the cases in the study by **Roy R et al., (2017)** had a stay of around 5 days. Thus, both the groups required almost same duration of hospital care.

There was no maternal death reported in any of the two groups of our study.

Apgar scores of neonates at 1st and 5th minutes were compared in the cases and controls and a significantly lower Apgar score was found in cases in this study (Table 10 & 11). Also, grand multiparous women were more likely to deliver babies with a low Apgar score (<7) as compared to non grand multiparous women.

Mgaya et al., (2013) concluded in his study that neonates delivered by grand multiparous women were at three-times greater risk of a low Apgar score compared with lower parity women. **Severinski N et al., (2009)** found a significantly higher incidence of low Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes in cases. Similarly, **Munim et al., (2000)** reported significantly low five-minute Apgar scores in the cases as compared to controls. This was concordant with our study results.

Unlike our result of Apgar score comparison, **Alhainiah et al., (2018)** did not find any significant difference in the two groups.

Another parameter used to compare perinatal outcome in this study was birth weight, which was found similar in the two groups. The mean birth weights of neonates of cases and controls was 2.76 ± 0.659 kg and 2.81 ± 0.469 kg, respectively (Table 12).

In contrast to this, **Alhainiah et al., (2018)** concluded that the average of the fetal weight of the newborn of grand multiparas was 6.067 ± 0.710 kg, which were heavier than those of controls and statistically significant with a p-value < 0.001. This may be attributed to a high incidence of gestational diabetes found in cases in this study.

Among the various perinatal complications compared between the two groups, the neonates of cases, as compared to those of controls, were found to have a significantly higher risk of prematurity, intra-uterine death, early neonatal death and low birth weight (Table 13).

The most significantly associated perinatal complication with grand multiparas in our study was intra-uterine death, with a P-value of 0.003. 19 grand multiparous women were admitted to the hospital with IUFDs during the study period. Such a high number of IUFDs may be attributed to the casual approach of most of the grand multiparas towards pregnancy and its possible complications, their lack of education and poor antenatal care.

In congruence to this, **Muniro et al., (2019)** demonstrated that grand multiparas had a higher risk of experiencing still births and preterm births as compared to women with lower parity. **Hoque et al., (2008)** also found a higher risk of intra-uterine fetal deaths in grand multiparas. However, **Eugene et al., (2019)** did not find any significant association between the two.

Another important perinatal complication found significantly associated with grand multiparity in our study was early neonatal death. This can be linked to the lower Apgar scores found in neonates of cases. Early neonatal demise has also been reported by **Ajong et al., (2019)** to be more frequently seen in cases than in controls. **Rizwan et al., (2009)** also noted a high incidence (35%) of perinatal deaths in GMPs.

Grand multiparous women in our study also had a higher incidence of preterm deliveries, with a significant P-value of 0.019. Some among them had gone into spontaneous preterm labour, some had spontaneous preterm rupture of membranes which was followed by induction of labour, and some had to be delivered prematurely in emergency because of complications. Similar results were seen by **Babinszki et al., (1999)**. Unlike our results, **AlKadri et al., (2016)** and **Omole-Ohonsi et al., (2009)** demonstrated no significant association between high parity and preterm births.

Low birth weight was another perinatal complication found significantly more frequent in cases in this study. A plausible explanation to this can be a high incidence of preterm births in cases of our study. **Eugene et al., (2019)**, however, did not find any significant association of LBW with grand multiparity. Also, **Al-Shaikh et al., (2017)** conversely found a higher association of LBW with primiparas as compared to grand multiparas.

Our study did not find any significant association of macrosomia with cases, which was in accordance to the study done by **Eugene et al., (2019)**. Also, intra-uterine growth retardation was found almost equally in both the groups of our study, which showed similarity with results of **Alhainiah et al., (2018)**.

Neonatal ICU admission was more frequently required for neonates of grand multiparous women as compared to lower parity women, in our study. This difference had a significant P-value of 0.034 (Table 14). The mean duration of stay in NICU was longer in neonates of cases than those of controls but it wasn't statistically significant (Table 15). Similar to this, neonatal admission to ICU was significantly higher in cases than controls in the study by **Al-Shaikh et al., (2017)**. **Munim et al., (2000)** also found a higher rate of NICU admission in cases but the difference was not significant statistically.

SUMMARY

&

CONCLUSION

The present study entitled “Grand multiparity and its feto-maternal outcomes in a tertiary care hospital” was conducted in the department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, SMGS Hospital, Government Medical College, Jammu with the aim to determine the prevalence of grand multiparity, to study the maternal and fetal outcome of grand-multiparous pregnancies.

In the present study, all the grand mutiparous women (cases) admitted in our hospital during the study period were compared with an equal number of women with 1st to 4th viable pregnancy (controls), chosen by systematic sampling.

Following key observations were made in the study:

- The prevalence of grand multiparity was 0.77%.
- Grand multiparous women were more likely to be of advanced age as compared to lower parity women.
- Grand multiparas had a higher chance of delivering at a lower gestational age than that of non grand multiparas.
- Most common mode of delivery in grand multiparas was vaginal.

- Antenatal complications significantly associated with grand multiparity were severe anemia and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy.
- Intra-partum complication significantly associated with grand multiparity was compound presentation.
- Post-partum complication significantly associated with grand multiparity was post-partum hemorrhage.
- Requirement of blood transfusions was significantly higher in grand-multiparous women as compared to non grand multiparas.
- Neonates of grand multiparas were more likely to have a lower Apgar score at 1 and 5 minutes, as compared to those of non grand multiparas.
- Perinatal complications significantly associated with grand multiparity were intra-uterine fetal death, preterm delivery, early neonatal death and low birth weight.
- Neonates of grand multiparas were significantly more at the risk of requirement of NICU admission.

LIMITATIONS:

1. These findings are not generalizable to the J&K population as this was a referral hospital based study and a large number of women in Jammu do not give birth inside a hospital or medical facility.
2. As this was a prospective study conducted for a short period of one year, long term complications of grand multiparity could not be studied.
3. Low rates of rare maternal and fetal outcomes in the two groups due to small sample size is a possible limitation to the statistical power of our analysis.
4. Due to a low number of admissions of patients in our hospital because of COVID-19 pandemic during the study period, the prevalence calculated might have been under estimated.
5. Many complications which have been associated with grand multiparity have also been independently associated with advanced maternal age. So, maternal age is an important confounder which must be controlled to minimize bias in the interpretation of results.

STRENGTHS:

This study is the first to reveal the prevalence of grand multiparity in Jammu and it provides a current picture on the prevalence and outcome of grand multiparity in this set up.

This study serves as the baseline data on maternal and perinatal outcomes associated with grand multiparity in the country upon which further studies could be referenced.

CONCLUSION:

Although the prevalence of grand multiparity is low in the present study, it still has been a high risk entity for both the mother and fetus in developing countries. Also, grand multiparity should not just be tackled purely as a health challenge but also as a socio-economic problem. Causes of complications in grand multiparity are multiple, complex and inter-related, but mostly preventable.

Present study shows that there is a significant increase in fetomaternal complications like anemia, hypertensive disorder, PPH, preterm deliveries, IUFD, etc. in these pregnancies, leading to severe morbidity in mother and fetus. Thus, there is a need for proper pregnancy evaluation, regular antenatal visits, intrapartum care and postnatal follow up to improve pregnancy outcome of all high risk pregnancies. In addition to this, we need to increase community awareness on its risks and encourage birth control among older women. Hospitals should be prepared and well equipped for emergency situation that can arise when attending deliveries of high parity group. Enhancement of existing government policies on reproductive and sexual health are needed to curb potential socioeconomic burden of grand multiparity in rural areas.

More studies, preferably with large enough sample sizes are recommended to validate these preliminary findings and evaluate adverse outcomes of grand multiparous deliveries.

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ABBREVIATIONS

- APH : Ante-Partum Hemorrhage
- ARDS : Acute respiratory distress syndrome
- C Section : Caesarean Section
- CPD : Cephalo-Pelvic Disproportion
- DM : Diabetes Mellitus
- GDM : Gestational Diabetes Mellitus
- G-HTN : Gestational Hypertension
- GMP : Grand Multiparity
- GMPs : Grand Multiparas
- HBsAg : Hepatitis B surface Antigen
- HELLP : Hemolysis, elevated liver enzymes, low platelet count
- HIV : Human Immunodeficiency Virus
- IUFD : Intra-Uterine Fetal Death
- IUGR : Intra-Uterine Growth Retardation
- LBW : Low Birth Weight
- LFTs : Liver Function Tests
- LSCS : Lower Segment Caesarean Section
- MAS : Meconium Aspiration Syndrome
- NICU : Neonatal Intensive Care Unit
- NPOL : Non-Progression of Labour

- PIH : Pregnancy Induced Hypertension
- PPH : Post-Partum Hemorrhage
- PPROM : Preterm Premature Rupture of Membranes
- PROM : Premature Rupture of Membranes
- PT : Prothrombin Time
- PTI : Prothrombin Index
- RFTs : Renal Function Tests
- ROM : Rupture of Membranes
- SD : Standard Deviation
- USG : Ultra Sonography
- VDRL : Venereal Disease Research Laboratory Test